

PROCEEDINGS BOOK

INTERNATIONAL MEDITERRANEAN CONGRESS

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

Edited by

Asst. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Emin KALGI

INTERNATIONAL
MEDITERRANEAN
CONGRESS

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

PROCEEDINGS BOOK

Edited by
Asst. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Emin KALGI

by
IKSAD GLOBAL PUBLISHING HOUSE

E-mail: info@iksad.com
izdasconference2@gmail.com www.izdas.org

All rights of this book belong to IKSAD GLOBAL Publishing House
Authors are responsible both ethically and juristically

IKSAD GLOBAL Publications – 2022©

Issued: 02.12.2022

ISBN:978-625-6380-19-6

CONGRESS ID

CONGRESS TITLE

INTERNATIONAL MEDITERRANEAN CONGRESS

DATE and PLACE

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

ORGANIZATION

IKSAD Institute

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Prof. Dr. Mykola VAS'KIV
Doç. Dr. Olha BYKOVA
Dr. Vedat AKMAN
Dr. Baurcan BOTAKARAYEV
Öğr. Gör. Cihan YETKİN
Elvan CAFAROV
Ali SÖYLEMEZ

NUMBER of ACCEPTED PAPERS

146

NUMBER of REJECTED PAPERS

35

PARTICIPANT COUNTRIES (21)

Türkiye, Morocco, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Nigeria, Iran, Vietnam, Azerbaijan, Lithuania, India, Indonesia, Algeria, Pakistan, Brazil, Portugal, Romania, South Africa, Spain, Ukraine, Malaysia, Taiwan

TOTAL NUMBER of INTERNATIONAL PAPERS

Türkiye (69), Other Countries (77)

EVALUATION PROCESS

All Applications Have Undergone A Double-Blind Peer Review Process

PRESENTATION

Oral Presentation

INTERNATIONAL
MEDITERRANEAN
CONGRESS

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

Proceedings Book

**METHODS AND TECHNIQUES FOR ELECTROMAGNETIC CHARACTERIZATION OF
DIELECTRICS AND FLEXIBLE CONDUCTORS**

**Andrey Souza Pinheiro^{*1,2}, Laiza Costa Santos Nascimento^{1,3}, Kenedy Marconi Geraldo dos Santos^{1,4},
Polyane Alves dos Santos^{1,5}, and Tagleorge Silveira Marques^{6,7,8}**

^{*1}Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Bahia, Vitória da Conquista, Brazil.

²ORCID 0000-0002-0409-939X

³ORCID 0000-0002-5753-7496

⁴ORCID 0000-0002-4980-7011

⁵ORCID 0000-0003-4724-9252

⁶ UA- University of Aveiro, DETI, Aveiro, Portugal,

⁷ ISTECS – Instituto Superior de Tecnologias Avançadas, Porto, Portugal,

⁸ ORCID 0000-0002-6776-6057

Abstract

Choosing the right material, through suitable methods, for an engineering project can make all the difference in the final cost of the product, in its development time and in the variety in which it can be used. Determining the electromagnetic characteristics of a material is of fundamental importance, especially under the use of technologies such as RFID (Radio Frequency Identification), 5G and Wi-Fi networks, which tend to be increasingly used with the advent of IoT (Internet of Things) and industry 4.0. Thus, performing an accurate electromagnetic characterization of materials suitable for technological applications is a necessity in the face of the new industrial revolution. Consequently, in order to design efficient radio frequency (RF) antennas or circuits, the dielectric and conductive properties of materials used as substrates or placed in their vicinity must be known, and these properties are usually extracted through electromagnetic material characterization methods and techniques. Since the relative permittivity ϵ_r , the relative permeability μ_r and the tangent of losses $\tan \delta$ of the material influence the propagation characteristics of the material, these constitutive parameters must be found and considered during circuit designs for microwave applications, having the main purpose is to reduce costs and errors in the final characteristics of a product.

Keywords: insulating materials, conductive materials, electromagnetic characteristics, resonant cavity.